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D1.1 - SPECIFICATIONS AND DEFINITION OF MATERIALS, COMPONENTS AND CELL DESIGN

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PROJECT GENERAL INFORMATION

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AF-SSB	Anode-free solid-state battery
BEA	Battery Electric Aircraft
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
BMS	Battery Management System
BoL	Begin of Life
CAM	Cathode active material
CC	Current collectors
DoD	Deep-of-Discharge
DST	Dynamic-Stress-Test
EA	Electronic additives
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EoL	End of Life
eVTOL	Electric Vertical Take-Off and Landing
HEA	Hybrid Electric Aircraft
HSPE	Hybrid solid polymer-based electrolyte
ICE	Internal Combustion Engine
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCC	Lithiophilic current collectors
LFP	Lithium Iron Phosphate, LiFePO_4
LiM-SSB	Lithium metal solid-state battery
LMA	Lithium metal anode
LMFP	Lithium Manganese Iron Phosphate, LiMnFePO_4
MLPC	Multi-layer pouch cell
NMC	Layered Mixed Transition Metal Oxide, LiNiMnCoO_2
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
P:E	Power-to-Energy ratio
PLD	Pulsed Laser Deposition
S-o-A	State-of-the-Art

SoC	State of Charge
SoH	State of Health
SSB	Solid State Batteries
VDC	Volts Direct Current
VGCF	Vapor Grown Carbon Fiber Nanofiber
WLTC	Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Cycle
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D1.1 describes technical and non-technical requirements for SSB and lists all design parameters and related KPIs for LiM-SSB and AF-SSB, as defined in Task 1.1 and Task 1.2 of WP1 in the SOLVE project.

In particular, CRF and PVS, the two main end-users of the project, provide the requirements for the cells according to the specific applications. These specifications overlap with the target of the call to define tentative KPIs for the cells developed within the project. Furthermore, CRF and PVS provide information about the cell module technical specification, which will be considered in the SOLVE prototype module design.

In addition, CID defines the material specifications for all cell technologies under development, aligning with the requirements outlined in the call and provided by the project's end users. This definition is completed for each cell component in collaboration with the partners responsible for their fabrication. Additionally, the cell design parameters are specified in accordance with the needs of the partners handling the final assembly.

Some of the data included in this deliverable is sensitive for the end users involved in the project, and as such, certain values have been kept confidential in this public version of the deliverable to protect their interests. However, all relevant data has been shared with CINEA's Project Officer to ensure compliance with the project's reporting and transparency requirements.

1. INTRODUCTION

In T1.1, end-users and battery manufacturer of the consortium worked with project partners to co-define the specifications of the two targeted SSB to fulfil the needs of the electromobility sector, starting from their own requirements related to the two main envisaged applications (i.e., automotive and aviation). The target was to define a list of KPIs for cells and for the module according to these requirements, also considering the target of the project's call. Starting from these targets and from the inputs collected amongst all the partners involved in materials development, T1.2 focuses on the design of LiM-SSB and AF-SSB cells, defining target characteristics of active and inactive materials and cell components (e.g. ratio, loading, density, thickness) to achieve the established cell performance KPIs.

In this deliverable all the outcomes of the two tasks are summarized, from the initial end-user specifications to the final cells design in order to provide a complete overview of the cell development process within the SOLVE project.

2. END-USER SPECIFICATION & KPIs DEFINITION

2.1. AUTOMOTIVE USER CASE

2.1.1. CELL REQUIREMENTS

A typical full-electric vehicle (BEV) is normally equipped with a battery pack that can store energy up to 40-250 kWh accordingly to the application, and a working electric potential between 300-400 V, with peaks up to 800 V for luxury/sport applications. The cells normally employed in this kind of application are Gen3 technologies (liquid electrolyte) with capacities between 80 and 200 Ah. Lower capacities would require a higher number of connections between cells, increasing the complexity of the battery pack architecture. In addition, the current trend oriented to increased range lead to progressive higher cell capacity, with peaks close to 300 Ah. Currently there is no "standard" cell design geometry defined for automotive applications and car manufacturers can easily integrate all variations (prismatic and pouch cells, but also cylindrical) taking into account their own advantages and disadvantages, such as weight and cost reduction.

Layered Mixed Transition Metal Oxide (LiNiMnCoO₂, NMC) vs. graphite is the most widespread cell chemistry in the automotive field, due to its acceptable safety and high specific energy, but the disadvantages of such technology (high price, critical raw material content, safety) are pushing to an increasingly widespread application of LFP chemistry. Despite its lower energy density, this chemistry is becoming very important in the automotive sector, in particular for small and low-cost vehicles (city car), thanks to the lower price, higher safety and lower impact from raw material sourcing. Strategies to improve its performances are already under development (e.g., LMFP and blends with NMC¹). At the anode side, the application of silicon is still limited in the automotive sector (less than 10% in combination with graphite) due to all the drawbacks of this technology, but several new high-Si solutions are reaching good level of maturity for a vehicle OEMs validation.

The use of SSBs in the automotive industry is a widely discussed topic, particularly due to their higher energy density, enhanced safety, and potentially lower manufacturing costs. There are also numerous bold claims about the significant advancements these technologies represent compared to current lithium-ion batteries. Practically speaking there is still a gap between these claims and the real application in vehicles and despite the first vehicle offerings based on SSB are beginning to emerge into the market, several limitations are still in place (no Li metal at the anode, durability not clear). These limits are reflected on the time needed to develop a reliable technology suitable for automotive application, with 8-10 years for "sample A" plus 3-6 further years for a complete commercialization. The primary challenges lie in the application of lithium metal, which offers significant potential for improving energy density but still involves higher manufacturing costs compared to the S-o-A and presents safety concerns. Additionally, the development of

game-changing solid electrolytes remains hindered by issues related to durability and complex manufacturing processes, including handling, defect reduction, and safety².

Despite all these drawbacks, SSBs represent a promising opportunity for the automotive field to increase the practical driving range, reducing the impact on weight of the vehicles. Vehicle OEMs are already deeply involved in SSB development projects in cooperation with battery and materials makers active in this field, to obtain reliable an applicable product despite the current long time required to upscale these kinds of technologies. In **Table 1** the main requirements for automotive SSB technologies are summarized:

Table 1: Automotive requirements for SSB technologies (2028 and 2030+ targets)

Feature	Unit	2028	2030+	Comments
Usable Specific Energy	Wh/kg			
Usable Energy Density	Wh/l			
10s Discharge @ 20%SoC	P:E			
30s Discharge @ 20%SoC	P:E			
Continuous Disch. @ 20%SoC	P:E			
10s Charge @ 90%SoC	P:E			
Charge Time	min			
Cycle Life @ 25°C	# cycle			
Operating Pressure	Bar			
Low Temperature	% Capacity			
Safety	EUCAR Level			

The targets are defined according to possible usability scenarios for automotive applications.

P:E (Power-to-Energy ratio) is a parameter that compares the instantaneous power output of a system to the total energy it can produce over a specific time period. This ratio is crucial in understanding the efficiency and performance of energy systems, especially in evaluating how effectively energy can be harnessed and stored.

In terms of cycle life, the EoL condition conventionally applied to automotive battery cells is 80% SoH. Apart the constant current cycling condition, performed conventionally at C/3, more practical tests can be applied. Specific charge/discharge profiles are designed to simulate the behaviour in conditions closer to real vehicle use, e.g. dynamic change and/or discharge rate with periodic charge spikes to simulate the regenerative braking that can occur in real world situations. The two profiles mainly applied are:

- **DST (Dynamic-Stress-Test):** A simplified version of Federal Urban Driving Schedule, a US standard, synthetic driving cycles used to replicate the real drive conditions. It is composed by a 360-second sequence of power steps with 7 discrete power levels, defined accordingly to the application under testing.

- **WLTC:** A power profile derived from the Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Procedure. The WLTC cycle was developed for the evaluation and homologation of emissions and fuel consumption on light-duty vehicles, under realistic driving conditions (urban, suburban, and highway driving) through four dynamic phases, standardizing parameters like speed, acceleration and vehicle set up. For the BEV, this cycle is applied to assess the energy consumption, range and efficiency, performing the cycle on the vehicle with a chassis-dyno bench test. During this test, the power profiles are recorded at the electric motor level, which is directly related to the energy exchanged from the battery pack during the execution. This profile can be scaled from battery pack to single cell level applying specific conversion factors linked to the pack architecture. In particular, the profile is downgraded considering the number of cells that compose the defined battery pack and the number of series/parallel connection between them and the single cell capacity.

For SOLVE cells testing campaign, the WLTC is selected as the power profile.

2.1.2. MODULE SPECIFICATION

Due to the drawbacks described in the previous section, the application of SSB in automotive battery packs and modules is very limited and so is the related information. To support the building of SOLVE's modules, based on the SSB cells developed within the project. **Table 2** lists the specification of a reference automotive battery module. This module is based on Gen3 S-o-A cells, NMC vs Graphite chemistry with a liquid electrolyte.

Table 2: Automotive battery module specifications.

Feature	Unit	Spec.	Comments
Nominal Energy	Wh		
Specific Energy	Wh/kg		
Operation Temperature Range Discharge	°C		
Operation Temperature Range Charge	°C		
Operation Voltage Range	V		
Maximum Charge Rate	C-rate		
Time Maximum Charge	sec		
SoC Operational Range	% SoC		
Maximum Discharge Rate	C-rate		
Time Maximum Discharge	sec		
Cycle Life	# cycle		
Cooling requirement	°C		

There is a clear technical gap between Gen3 and Gen4 cells from the module application point of view. Therefore, the specifications provided for the automotive use case (**Table 2**) show what are the current end-user needs based on Gen3. However, the requirements of the modules (assembled in WP4) will only fulfil the project requirements, as they represent a proof of concept for 6 cells assembled (10 Ah LiM-SSB) in a mini-module with nominal energy of 0.25 kWh.

2.2. AVIATION USER CASE

2.2.1. CELL SPECIFICATION

In the aeronautical sector, three main categories of target vehicles must be considered to improve S-o-A solutions. To encompass a wide spectrum of use-case applications, Battery Electric Aircraft (BEA), Hybrid Electric Aircraft (HEA), and Electric Vertical Take-Off and Landing (eVTOL) vehicles are included in the cell specification definition. Based on the performance characteristics of the aircraft—such as maximum take-off mass, required power, aerodynamic configuration, and environmental conditions—a unified set of specifications is established at the pack level. These pack-level specifications are subsequently translated into cell-level requirements to meet the end-user needs of aeronautical applications. In the following sections, a brief explanation of the target vehicle is provided.

- BEA: the lower business segment of aviation primarily consists of propeller-driven aircraft in general aviation, where all performance requirements are met using a purely electric energy storage system.
- HEA: due to the technological limitations of battery cells, HEA is widely implemented in the upper business segment of the aviation sector such as commuter and regional aircraft.
- eVTOL: focused on vertical take-off and landing compared to the conventional aircraft type on runway. Mainly applicable for Urban Air Mobility.

Velis Electro is the 2-seater propeller driven all electric aircraft designed by PVS. It consists of 2 battery packs with rated energy of 10 kWh each. The propulsion system is based on 400 V architecture. Therefore, the maximum voltage of the battery is designed around 400 VDC. The Velis Electro's proprietary BMS (Battery Management System) features various protective layers in order to operate the battery during nominal as well as off-nominal conditions. In **Figure 1**, an illustration of the Velis Electro is provided.

Figure 1. Velis Electro is the world's first electric powered airplane to receive a type certificate.

In the following section, the related characterizations of the battery cell specifications for each type of aircraft category are explained.

In general, mass plays an important role in aircraft design. Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) based aircraft are designed with the considerations of the typical aviation fuel. Therefore, significant improvement is required to achieve the comparable specific energy and energy density targets. Aircraft range and endurance are key parameters in lower as well as upper business segments. In addition, safety is crucial in civil aviation. For example, the Velis Electro is mostly operated under A-A flight conditions. In this condition, a pilot is well aware of his destination, and standard procedures can be performed in case of an emergency. However, typical A-B flights involve unknown flight spaces with limited visual conditions. Therefore, regulatory standards require additional flight time to compensate for extra workload that is needed for the

pilot to safely land the aircraft. Range and endurance requirements are more significant in aircrafts that fall under upper business segment.

Along with gravimetric energy density, volumetric energy density also needs to be considered especially during the initial phase of the battery cell development. Due to the performance improvements that can be achieved by incorporating the battery modules inside the wing section, higher volumetric energy density is required in lower business segment of aviation.

Both conventional fixed-wing and rotorcraft require higher excess power during the take-off, initial-climb and go-around flight phases. Although technical possibilities are available to recharge the batteries, e.g. during descent and approach phases, there are regulatory hurdles behind these solutions. Therefore, the battery cells operate mostly in higher Depth of Discharge (DoD) conditions. To achieve safe operation in these flight phases, maintaining a constant current is essential. At lower State of Charge (SoC), the battery's internal resistance tends to increase, which can result in a rapid drop in terminal voltage. To prevent deep discharge and allow adequate power generation, peak power density parameters are considered in lower SoC window. To achieve other flight phases, such as cruise and landing, reduced power density is considered in lower DoD window. Subsequently, complete SoH of the battery must be taken into account because it affects the amount of energy (SoC) used in each flight phase.

In HEA category, batteries are considered as the secondary source of power during an abnormal condition, such as failure of a primary subsystem within the fuel cell, which can result in one engine inoperative. Therefore, the power density requirements are significantly higher.

Battery cell degradation is primarily affected by higher charge and discharge rates especially below 0°C operating temperatures. Although, additional deratings are incorporated in Velis Electro chargers due to safety reasons, higher charging capabilities are required to comply with the customer needs. This will significantly reduce the lead time and increase the operational utilization of the aircraft. HEA and eVTOL applications require less than 30 minutes charge time to reduce the turnaround time. In addition, aircrafts are mostly stored in the hanger without any utilization.

For aeronautical applications, RTCA DO-311A and DO-160G provide minimum operational performance standards and define environmental conditions. Moreover, European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) established means of compliance with the special condition VTOL to identify the substantial progress been made in the development and integration of rechargeable lithium batteries with novel chemistries in aviation. Therefore, these regulatory standards are used to validate the safety and reliability of the battery cells.

All specifications for SSB technologies are summarized and provided in the **Table 3**.

Table 3: Aeronautical requirements for SSB technologies.

Feature	Unit	Spec.	Comments
Usable Specific Energy	Wh/kg		
Specific Energy	Wh/L		
Power Density (Continues)	W/kg		
Power Density (Peak)	W/kg		
Max. Continues Disch.	C-rate		
Max. Peak Disch.	C-rate		
Standard Charge Rate	C-rate		
Cycle Life	#cycle		
Operating Pressure	Bar		
Self-discharge	%		
Safety			

2.2.2. MODULE SPECIFICATION

The cell level requirements are defined based on the module level consideration. The top-down design methodology is applied to systematically specify the module as well as cell level end user requirements.

The design focuses on lightweight energy storage, efficient thermal management, and long-term durability, meeting the rigorous demands for electric aviation. The battery module provides a nominal energy of 1037 Wh, achieved through a 24S1P cell configuration (~12 Ah capacity). With a specific energy of 320 Wh/kg, the module is optimized for lightweight applications, ensuring minimal impact on aircraft payload and efficiency considering range and endurance.

The module is designed to operate under diverse environmental conditions:

- Discharge temperature range: -20 °C to +60 °C.
- Charge temperature range: 0 °C to +45 °C.

Thermal management is supported by a coolant operating temperature range of -8 °C to +42 °C, ensuring safe and efficient performance under various operating scenarios.

The module operates at a nominal voltage of 86 VDC, within an operational range of 62–100 VDC. It supports a maximum charge rate of 1C. A maximum discharge rate of 4C allows for high-power demands, such as take-off or climbing phases as well as go-around flight phases.

The battery module offers a cycle life of over 1000 cycles, ensuring long-term operational reliability.

An overview of these specifications is provided in **Table 4**.

Table 4: Aeronautical battery module specifications.

	Unit	Spec.	Comments
Nominal Energy	Wh	1037	Based on cell config. 24S1P (~12 Ah)
Specific Energy	Wh/kg	> 320	
Operation Temperature Range Discharge	°C	-20 /+60	
Operation Temperature Range Charge	°C	0 /+45	
Operation Voltage Range	V	86 VDC (nominal) 62 - 100 VDC	
Maximum Charge Rate	C-rate	1	
Time Maximum Charge	sec	3600	
SoC Operational Range	% SoC	0-100%	
Maximum Discharge Rate	C-rate	4	Continuous
Time Maximum Discharge	sec	N/A	Unknown, it depends on power consumption
Cycle Life	# cycle	> 1000	
Cooling requirement	°C	-8 / +42	Coolant operating temperature

2.3. BATTERY CELLS KPIS DEFINITION

The KPIS for the cells developed within the SOLVE project are defined starting from the requirements provided by the end-users involved, CRF and PVS. The KPIS were also defined considering the target of the project's call, HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02-01, summarized in **Table 5**:

Table 5: HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02-01 target parameters (at cell level).

Feature	Unit	Target	Comments
Usable Specific Energy	Wh/kg	> 400	
Usable Energy Density	Wh/l	> 1000	
Cycle Life	# cycle	3000 > 500	50% DoD 80% DoD
Maximum Charge Rate	C-rate	5	10C for aviation
Charge Time	min	< 20	Till full capacity recovery
Safety	EUCAR Level	≤ 4	

Considering the differences between the two applications under analysis, i.e. automotive and aviation, two different sets of KPIS were defined, in order to have target values specific for two scenarios which are listed in **Table 6**:

Table 6: KPIS list for automotive and aviation user-case scenarios.

KPI	Parameter	Unit	Automotive		Aviation	
			Target	Comments	Target	Comments
1	Usable Specific Energy	Wh/kg	> 400	@BoL 90%SoC - C/3	>445	@BOL 15% SoC - 1C
2	Usable Energy Density	Wh/l	> 1000	@BoL 90%SoC - C/3	>1350	@BOL 15% SoC - 1C
3	Cycle Life	# cycle	> 1500	C/3 - WLTP cycles (EoL =80% SoH)	>1000	EoL = 0% SoH (Fast charge, fast disch., school laps)
4	Maximum Charge Rate	C-rate	5		10	
5	Charge Time	min	< 10	20-80% SoC	< 20	0-100% SoC
6	Safety	EUCAR Level	≤ 4		RTCA DO-311A & 160G	
7	Operational pressure	MPa	≤ 0.1		≤ 0.1	

3. MATERIALS, COMPONENTS AND CELL DESIGN DEFINITION

Task 1.2 is dedicated to the definition of all materials, components and cell designs to be used in the assembly of the SOLVE battery cells. The specifications for all components are considered in accordance with various battery cells KPIs identified for the call in Section 2.3 of this report. The target of the project is to develop two cell technologies, i.e. Lithium metal SSB (LiM-SSB) and Anode-free SSB (AF-SSB). Cells in both technologies will be assembled in WP4 with cell sizes of 10 and 20 Ah for LiM-SSB and 5 and 10 Ah for AF-SSB. The assembly of the cells with different sizes and technologies will be done by CID and SAFT. CID will assemble LiM-SSB and AF-SSB with cell sizes of 10 Ah and 5 Ah, respectively, via manual assembly. In turn, SAFT will assemble LiM-SSB and AF-SSB with cell sizes of 20 Ah and 10 Ah, respectively, via automatic assembly line.

It is important to carefully identify all materials and cell components to be used in final prototypes based on the feasibility and technical limitations of each partner. The selection process has been carried out systematically for each of the cell components by all partners involved in WP1. All the materials, components and cell design specifications are available to all the partners in the SharePoint of the SOLVE consortium.

This section of the deliverable D1.1 establishes technical specifications for the components of the cells, which will ensure that all partners have access to the roadmap to achieve the defined project targets.

3.1. MATERIAL AND COMPONENT DEFINITION

Technical specifications related to materials and components have been structured with emphasis on achieving all defined targets in terms of energy density and cycle life for both cell technologies. Careful considerations have been made to verify the compatibility and durability of all materials and components, with due attention given to their integration within the overall system of all project partners.

Given the combinations arising from two distinct cell technologies and cell sizes for each format, it is essential to establish a comprehensive definition to facilitate the preparation of a detailed roadmap. This roadmap should outline the specific requirements for each cell format and size combination, ensuring accomplishment of call requirements. This approach will help in providing guidance throughout the project to allow for timely adjustments to reduce risks related to component and cell performance.

Figure 2. Different components to be used in assembling LiM-SSB and AF-SSB (Source: SOLVE grant agreement document - [101147094] [SOLVE] – Part B).

Figure 2 depicts the different components on both cell technologies, with both formats sharing similar cathode and hybrid solid polymer electrolyte (HSPE) properties such as cathode areal capacity and HSPE formulation. It should be noted that both cell technologies will consist of double side coated cathode and

anodes. **Table 7** summarizes the components to be used in different cell technologies, which will also be utilised to fabricate and assemble three modules, as well as the responsible partners for their development.

Table 7: Summary of the components to be used in different cell technologies and partners responsible for their fabrication.

Part	Component	Target	Responsible partners	
High loading solid-state cathode	Aluminium current collector	$\delta \leq 15 \mu\text{m}$	CIDETEC (CID)	
	Active material	$(Q_{\text{dis}} > 200 \text{ mAh/g}, \text{LL} > 4 \text{ mAh/cm}^2)$ <i>Wet and dry-processing</i>	Fraunhofer IKTS (IKTS)	
	Electronic additives		Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives (CEA)	
	Catholyte			
Electrolyte	Hybrid ceramic polymer electrolyte	Ionic conductivity $\geq 0.5 \text{ mS/cm}$, Electrochemical stability $\geq 4.7 \text{ V}$, $\delta \leq 30 \mu\text{m}$ <i>Dry processing</i>	Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) ARKEMA (ARK) Fraunhofer IKTS (IKTS)	
Anode LiM-SSB	Lithium coated copper foil	Ultra-thin Li-metal foil & protective engineered interface $\delta \sim 1\text{-}10 \mu\text{m}$ <i>Pulsed laser deposition</i>	Papierfabrik Wattens GMBH & CO KG (DLF) Oerlikon Surface Solutions AG (OSS) Tampereen Korkeakoulusaatio SR (TAU) Pulsedeon OY (PUL)	 delfort
Anode AF-SSB	Lithophilic current collector (LCC) AF-SSB	(1) Lithiophilic & barrier layer on Cu CC <i>Sputter deposition:</i> S3P™ ($\leq 2 \mu\text{m}$) & LPPS™ (5-10 μm) (2) Metallized cellulose-based lithiophilic CC <i>Pulsed laser deposition (1-20 μm)</i>	Tampereen Korkeakoulusaatio SR (TAU) Pulsedeon OY (PUL)	

3.1.1. CATHODE MATERIAL DEFINITION

The high-loading solid-state cathode is one of the most important components of the unit cell, which greatly influences energy density and durability, and needs to be clearly defined as per the call requirements. The catholyte in a composite cathode refers to the solid medium through which ions pass, though in these systems, the formulation of the catholyte is often closer to that of the solid-state electrolytes. The composition of the catholyte is important for the efficiency, stability, and energy density of the electrochemical system. The catholyte plays an essential role in facilitating ion movement and electrochemical reactions at the cathode during charge and discharge. In this task, cathode material definition included: (i) active material definition, (ii) inactive material definition, (iii) cathode geometry and formulation and (iv) cathode processing routes. defines the material and components to be used in fabrication of high-loading cathodes (>4 mAh/cm²) in the SOLVE project.

Active material definition included identification of commercial cathode active materials (CAM) and suitable CAM coating materials. Nickel-rich NMC and lithium-manganese-rich CAM were selected for LiM-SSB and AF-SSB cells, respectively. Both CAM were carefully chosen for their respective higher intrinsic specific capacity (~ 200 mAh/g and ~ 220 mAh/g) and charge cut-off voltage (4.4 V and 4.8 V), which is necessary to achieve the energy density targets specified in **Table 5**. To prevent oxidation of the electrolyte/catholyte in contact with cathode active material at high operational voltages, essential coating materials were specified for the CAM particles. The coating materials were determined based on their compatibility with both CAM and HSPE components. IKTS is responsible for supplying the coated CAM for cathode fabrication.

Further material specifications and formulations were identified for inactive components of the cathode such as electronic additives (EA) and polymeric catholyte. In high loading (>4 mAh/cm²) non-porous cathodes, catholyte performs the critical role of facilitating efficient Li⁺ transport network along with high electronic and ionic conductivity and excellent electrical contact between active cathode material particles. CID is responsible for the optimization of catholyte formulation with feedback from POLITO and ARK on the electrochemical performance along with other components in the cells.

The SOLVE project also deals with the manufacturing and optimization of these high-loading cathodes via two processing routes: (i) wet slurry-coating processing and (ii) dry extrusion-lamination process. Therefore, the definition of parameters for both processing routes is vital to the continuous improvement and fabrication of high-loading cathodes. The cathode formulations for coated CAM particles, EA and catholyte via each processing routes, which play an important role in the final electrochemical performance, were also defined under cathode geometry field in CID is responsible for the optimization and scale up of cathode via wet processing route. CEA is responsible for the evaluating and optimising the dry extrusion processing route.

Table 8: Material and components definition for high-loading cathode in SOLVE project.

Parameters		LiM-SSB		AF-SSB	
		10 Ah	20 Ah	5 Ah	10 Ah
Material specifications for wet processing of cathode					
Active material	Powder	Type:	Ni-rich NMC - (Ni > 80%)		Li-rich NMC
		Crystallinity:	Single crystal		Single crystal
		PSD modality:	Unimodal		Unimodal
		Chemical composition:	LiNi _{0.85} Mn _{0.05} Co _{0.10} O ₂		Li _{1.23} Ni _{0.10} Mn _{0.56} Co _{0.10} O ₂
		Specific capacity (mAh/g):	>200 (based on C-rates)		>220 (based on C-rates)
		Particle size - D50 (µm):	3-5		3-5
Coating	Thickness (nm)	≤ 0.1		≤ 0.1	
	Materials:	Li ₃ BO ₃ or Li ₂ ZrO ₃		Li ₃ BO ₃ or Li ₂ ZrO ₃	
Conductive additives	Type of additives:	Carbon black; VGCF		Carbon black; VGCF	
	Electronic conductivity (S/cm):	>0.005		>0.005	
Inactive material	Catholyte (for slurry processing)	Formulation (%) -polymer:	3-5		3-5
		Formulation (%) – Li salts:	3-5		3-5
		Formulation (%) -Plasticizers:	10-15		10-15
		Electrochemical stability limit (V):	> 4.7 V vs Li ⁺ /Li		> 4.7 V vs Li/Li ⁺ (1st Cycle 5.0 V vs Li ⁺ /Li)
		Ionic conductivity (mS/cm) at 25°C:	≥ 1		≥ 1
Cathode geometry (for slurry processing)	Formulation (%)	Current collector type:	Carbon coated Al foil		Carbon coated Al foil
		Current collector thickness (µm):	≤ 14		≤ 14
		Cathode active material:	≥ 70		≥ 70
		Conductive additive:	≤ 5		≤ 5
		Catholyte:	≤ 25		≤ 25
		Areal capacity (mAh/cm ²):	≥ 4		≥ 4
		Mass loading (mg/cm ²):	25-35		25-35
		Density (g/cm ³):	≥ 3		≥ 3
Number of sides coated:	2		2		

		Electronic conductivity (S/cm):	> 0.1	> 0.1
		Preparation procedure:	Slurry – roll to roll	Slurry – roll to roll
		Width of coated area (mm):	≥ 100	≥ 100
		CC sheet dimension (L x W - mm) - without tabs:	173.5 x 83	173.5 x 83
			98 x 58	173.5 x 83
Material specifications for dry processing of cathode				
Inactive materials	Conductive additives	Type of additive:	Carbon black; VGCF	Carbon black; VGCF
		Electronic conductivity (S/cm):	>0.005	>0.005
	Catholyte (for dry processing)	Formulation (%) -polymer:	3-5	3-5
		Formulation (%) – Li salts:	3-5	3-5
		Formulation (%) -Plasticizers:	10-15	10-15
		Electrochemical stability limit (V):	> 4.7 V vs Li ⁺ /Li	> 4.8 V vs Li/Li ⁺ (1 st cycle 5.0 V vs Li ⁺ /Li)
	Ionic conductivity (mS/cm) at 25°C:	≥1	≥1	
Cathode geometry (for dry processing)	Formulation (%)	Current collector type:	Carbon coated Al foil	Carbon coated Al foil
		Current collector thickness (µm):	≤ 14	≤ 14
		Cathode active material:	≥ 70	≥ 70
		Conductive additive:	≤ 5	≤ 5
		Catholyte:	≤ 25	≤ 25
		Areal capacity (mAh/cm ²):	≥ 4	≥ 4
		Mass loading (mg/cm ²):	25-35	25-35
		Density (g/cm ³):	≥ 3	≥ 3
Cathode processing parameters		Number of sides coated:	2	2
		Electronic conductivity (S/cm):	> 0.1	> 0.1
		Preparation procedure:	Extrusion (mixing) + lamination	Extrusion (mixing) + lamination
		Pilot line - Max. coating width (mm):	200	200
		Processing temperature (°C):	ca. 90	ca. 90
		CC sheet dimension (L x W - mm) - without tabs:	173.5 x 83	173.5 x 83
			98 x 58	173.5 x 83

3.1.2. HYBRID SOLID POLYMER ELECTROLYTE MATERIAL DEFINITION

An electrolyte facilitates the flow of electricity in external circuit by enabling ionic conduction, but it acts as an electronic insulator. Compared to standard liquid electrolytes, a solid-state electrolyte has the advantages of non-volatilization, mechanical and thermal stability, no issues of leakages of toxic organic solvents, so no corrosion and no explosion, thus absolute safety and greatly reduced reaction activity with lithium metal, along with easy processability, low self-discharge, higher achievable power density and cyclability.

Hybrid solid polymer-based electrolyte (HSPE) entails various functions, including maintaining good interfacial contact with both Li metal anode and thick solid-state cathode as well as suppressing Li dendrites growth during cycling. In this task, electrolyte material definition included: (i) solid polymer electrolyte definition, (ii) filler material definition, (iii) HSPE definition and (iv) upscaling of HSPE. **Table 9** defines the material and components used in fabrication of HSPE in the SOLVE project.

Since HSPE consists of a polymer-rich matrix, definition of formulation for polymeric electrolyte matrix is carried out in the first phase. The definition step is based on considerations to ensure high ionic conductivity at room temperature and compatibility with both high energy 4 V-class CAM and Li metal. The charge/discharge C-rate capability in “Li metal anode/HSPE/cathode” cells is factored into component definition. The thickness of the electrolyte is planned to be lower than 30 μm to meet the energy density requirements in the project. POLITO is responsible for definition of materials and components in HSPE. The impact of adding ceramic fillers to HSPE will also be evaluated to determine their effect on improving mechanical properties. IKTS is responsible for the synthesis of ceramic fillers based on requirements defined for HSPE. For fabrication of cells in SOLVE, optimized solid electrolyte formulation will be established initially to scale up manufacturing processes through a dry, solvent-free extrusion and lamination method. ARK is responsible for optimization and scale up of HSPE via dry processing route, likely extrusion.

Table 9: Material and component definition of HSPE in SOLVE project.

Parameters		LiM-SSB		AF-SSB		
		10 Ah	20 Ah	5 Ah	10 Ah	
Electrolyte geometry	Formulation (wt%)	Polymer	10-30			
		Li salt	10-20			
		Plasticizers	40-80			
		Ceramic filler	0-40			
	Ceramic fillers	Materials	Li _{1.3} Al _{0.3} Ti _{1.7} (PO ₄) ₃			
		Coating	Yes			
		Ionic conductivity of ceramic pellet (mS/cm)	> 0.5			
		Particle size - D50 (µm)	<1.0			
		Electrolyte Density (g/cm ³)	≥ 1.5			
		Porosity of electrolyte membrane	< 5%			
Electrolyte processing parameter	Electrochemical stability limit (V)	≥ 4.7				
	Ionic conductivity (mS/cm) at 25°C	≥ 0.5				
	Electrolyte dimension (L x W - mm)	189 x 88	189 x 88	110 x 70	189 x 88	
	Thickness (µm)	<30 + 10%				
	Width of electrolyte (mm)	110 max.				
	Temperature of processing (°C)	< 140				
	Electrolyte preparation procedure	Solvent-free, extrusion targeted				

3.1.3. ANODE MATERIAL DEFINITION

The two cell technologies being developed in SOLVE project differ from each other based on the anode being used in the cell. For LiM-SSB technology, using advanced Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) processing technology will enable manufacturing of ultra-thin lithium metal foils (LMA) with thickness of deposited lithium up to 10 μm , reducing required lithium quantity by over 80% compared to conventional Li foil extrusion processes (thickness $>30 \mu\text{m}$) which has some challenges such as high defect rate, requirements for high pressure and temperature during production. In the LiM-SSBs assembled in SOLVE, LMA will be used to assemble cells with 10 and 20 Ah capacity. In AF-SSB technology, the advantage in sustainability efforts gained from the usage of ultra-thin PLD processed lithium metal anode can further increase with usage of innovative cellulose-based lithiophilic current collector (LCC). The LCC technology not only targets at eliminating lithium excess in the cell but also reduce the usage of copper as current collector, increasing the foothold of anode-free concept into the market. In the AF-SSBs assembled in SOLVE, lithiophilic layer coated current collectors and cellulose-based lithiophilic current collectors will be utilized to assemble cells with 5 and 10 Ah capacity.

In this task, ultra-thin LiM based anode was selected based on specifications of: (i) current collector, (ii) Li metal/alloy deposition, and (iii) protective layer. On the other hand, Li-free anodes were chosen based on specifications of: (i) current collector, (ii) lithiophilic layer, (iii) barrier layer, and (iv) metallization concepts. **Table 10** defines the materials and components that will be used in the fabrication of both types of anodes. An important input for anode development was the limitation of solid state cell assembly partner (SAFT) on the minimum thickness of the current collector used to be more than 8 microns.

Ultra-thin lithium-based anodes utilized in LiM-SSB's were defined considering the type of current collectors (CC) used, Li metal deposition thickness, usage of Li-alloy stabilizing metals and additional lithium protection layers. To achieve the targeted energy density values, Li metal will be deposited as coating of thickness up to 10 μm on copper foil ($> 8 \mu\text{m}$) as current collector. PUL and TAU are responsible for optimizing the different layers and materials and deposition on current collectors of different sizes.

Lithiophilic CC based anodes utilized in AF-SSB were divided into two approaches: (i) lithiophilic layers deposited on conventional current collectors and (ii) lightweight cellulose-based lithiophilic current collectors (LCC). The material definition for conventional CC with lithiophilic layers and cellulose-based LCC was based on feedstock, process parameters, control atmosphere and substrate movement. Lightweight metallized cellulose-based LCC is also chosen for two different metallization concepts. OSS is responsible for the development and optimization of lithiophilic layers deposited on conventional CCs. PUL, DLF and TAU are responsible for the development and optimization of cellulose-based LCC.

Table 10: Material and component definition of anodes in the SOLVE project.

Parameters		LiM-SSB		AF-SSB		
		10 Ah	20 Ah	5 Ah	10 Ah	
Ultra-thin Li-metal foil	Current collector (CC)	Type of current collector (CC)	Cu, both sides polished			
		Thickness of CC (μm)	6-10			
		Limitations by partners:	SAFT – CC thickness should be $>8 \mu\text{m}$			
		Preparation procedure:	as received			
	Li metal layer	CC sheet dimension (L x W - mm) - without tabs	181.5 x 87	181.5 x 87		
		Number of sides - Li metal deposition:	2			
		Li metal deposition configuration:	R2R-PLD Li / Cu (CC) / R2R-PLD Li			
		Li metal deposition thickness (μm):	1-10			
		Li metal coating dimension (mm):	181.5 x 87	181.5 x 87		
		Alloying elements:	In, Mg			
Thin Copper foil	Metallized paper LCC	Alloying ratio by volume (xx: Li):	1:50 - 1:1			
		Alloying configuration:	PLD (in situ / same process cycle)			
		Thickness of barrier layer:	$\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$			
		Configuration of barrier layer:	LLZO by PLD on Li metal (same vacuum process cycle) alternate Li_3N , LiPON by PLD			
Lithiophilic current collector (LCC)	Thin Copper foil	Thickness of copper foil (μm):	< 10			
		Limitations by partners:	SAFT – CC thickness should be $>8 \mu\text{m}$			
		Active area dimension (L x W mm) - without tab:	100 x 60	181,5 x 87		
	Metallized paper LCC	Thickness of lithiophilic layer (μm):	< 3			
		Thickness of barrier layer:	$\sim 0.2 \mu\text{m} / 0.5 \mu\text{m} / 1 \mu\text{m}$			
		Configuration of barrier layer:	LLZO (dense) / Metal [Ag, Sn, Mg] / Paper / Metal [Ag, Sn, Mg] / LLZO (dense)			
		Thickness of substrate (μm):	12-35			
Metallized paper LCC	Porosity (%):	30-70				
	Air permeability:	5-100 s for 100 ml				

Metallized paper dimension (L x W - mm)
Metallization configuration 1
Metallization configuration 2
Thickness of metallized paper
Electrical conductivity (in plane)

100 x 60	181.5 x 87
R2R-PLD Metal [Ag, Sn, Mg] - Paper - R2R-PLD Metal [Ag, Sn, Mg]	
Post-processing by calendaring and/or thermally	
Dense metal layer, 1-3 μm	
(R2R-PLD LLZO -) R2R-PLD Mg - Paper - R2R PLD Mg (- R2R-PLD LLZO)	
Porous (40-60%) Mg layer, 2-20 μm	
LLZO (<2 μm) by PLD on porous Mg	
14-40 μm (conf 1); 20-60 μm (conf 2)	
Sufficient for handling required currents	

3.2. CELL-DESIGN DEFINITION

After optimizing and validating the individual cell components according to the material definitions outlined in Section 3.1, the top-performing formulations and components will be selected, scaled-up, and transferred to the assembly processes at CID and SAFT for multi-layer pouch cell (MLPC) production. This process marks a crucial step towards the development of high-performance solid state cells for the SOLVE project. The pouch cell assembly process will begin with benchmarking the upscaled components in smaller 0.5 Ah and 1 Ah cell formats. This initial phase will focus on evaluating the performance of the scaled-up components under controlled conditions to ensure they meet the project's specifications. As these smaller cells are optimized for performance, the next step will involve scaling up to larger-format MLPCs to test the components' behaviour in larger format cells. This two-step approach ensures that any issues are addressed at an early stage before proceeding to full-scale production.

The manual assembly of MLPC prototypes with 10 Ah LiM-SSB and 5 Ah AF-SSB cells will take place at CID facilities, where the components will be carefully handled to ensure that each cell meets its performance targets. At the same time, larger prototypes of 20 Ah LiM-SSB and 10 Ah AF-SSB will be assembled at SAFT, utilizing their automated cell assembly line for efficient and precise production ensuring scalability and consistency across batches.

Table 11 gathers the main features of different cell formats.

Table 11. Cell design specifications for assembly of multi-layered pouch cells.

Cell Size		10 Ah - AF-SSB	20 Ah - LiM-SSB	5 Ah - AF-SSB	10 Ah - LiM-SSB
Format		MLPC	MLPC	MLPC	MLPC
Responsible partner					
Assembly procedure		Automatized assembly		Manual assembly	
Number of cells to be assembled		15	25	40	75
Cell stacking Configuration		Anode/Cathode/ Anode	Anode/Cathode/ Anode	Anode/Cathode/ Anode	Anode/Cathode/ Anode
Cathode	Composition	Composite cathode with coated Li-rich CAM + e ⁻ conductor + catholyte	Composite cathode with coated Ni-rich CAM + e ⁻ conductor + catholyte	Composite cathode with coated Li-rich CAM + e ⁻ conductor + catholyte	Composite cathode with coated Ni-rich CAM + e ⁻ conductor + catholyte
	Number	9	18	12	9
Composition		HSPE	HSPE	HSPE	HSPE

Electrolyte	Number	18	36	22	18
	Composition	LCC	Li plated Cu foil with protective layers	LCC	Li plated Cu foil with protective layers
Anode	Number	10	19	11	10
	Electrode tab position	Opposite edge	Opposite edge	Same edge	Opposite edge

Based on the conclusions from **Table 11** and previous sections, SAFT has developed a similar design for both the 10 Ah AF-SSB and 20 Ah LiM-SSB pouch cells, ensuring that both cell types can be produced using the same production line. This approach guarantees that the 10 Ah and 20 Ah cell sizes will meet the energy density targets required by the SOLVE project. Moreover, it promotes uniformity in the production process, enabling all partners to produce similarly sized components for both cell types. This standardization is essential for minimizing variability in cell performance and ensuring efficient upscaling. CID will also adopt this design to manually assemble the 10 Ah LiM-SSB cells, maintaining the same electrode dimensions. The only difference will be in the number of unit cells used for different sizes, ensuring that the cell configuration remains consistent across different production formats.

For the manual assembly of 5 Ah AF-SSB cells at CID, the previous design was found to be impractical due to the resultant low thickness, which could hinder the ease of handling and the cell's overall structural integrity (**Figure 3**). To resolve this issue, the electrode dimensions were adjusted to a bigger size (60 x 100 mm²). This modification enhances the ease of handling during assembly and simultaneously improves the energy density of the cell, ensuring that it remains efficient upon operation without compromising structural stability. Additionally, across all cell formats, the lithium metal anode and HSPE will be designed to have slightly larger dimensions compared to that of composite cathode. This overhang of Li metal anode and HSPE ensures good alignment of the cell stacks, preventing accidental short-circuiting and being able to access the entire surface of the composite cathode during cycling. As the project progresses, each work package will incorporate more conditions and advanced components, pushing the limits of the cell designs and their performance capabilities.

Figure 3. Cell design for 5 Ah cells used at CID.

Summarizing this section, the optimization and validation of individual cell components will successfully lead to the selection and scaling-up of top-performing formulations for multi-layer pouch cell (MLPC) assembly at CID and SAFT. The initial benchmarking of upscaled components in 0.5 Ah and 1 Ah cells sets the stage for the subsequent preparation of larger-format MLPCs. CID will manually assemble 10 Ah LiM-SSB and 5 Ah AF-SSB prototypes, while SAFT will handle the automated assembly of larger 20 Ah LiM-SSB and 10 Ah AF-SSB cells. The consistent design approach across both manual and automated assembly lines ensures compatibility and meets the energy density targets of the SOLVE project.

The choice of electrode dimensions of cells optimizes handling and energy density while maintaining alignment and minimizing the risk of misalignment or short circuits. As the project progresses, advanced materials and components will be integrated, ensuring continuous improvement in performance and scalability, contributing to the overall success of the project.

CONCLUSIONS

This document summarized the data collection work done to define the cell designs and the material requirements accordingly to the potential use cases. In particular, starting from the project call and from the information provided by the two end users (CRF – automotive, PVS – aviation) a list of potential KPIs was defined to drive the SSB technologies development along the SOLVE project.

Starting from that, CID with the cooperation of all the key partners in charge for the material development, collected all the requirements for every cell component. From these, a cell design for both technologies (LiM-SSB and AF-SSB) has been defined with the cooperation of the partners in charge for the components production and cell assembly steps.

For the module both end users provided their respective specification, which were based on Gen3 cells, to give a general overview of the current status on this topic, but the target for the module development that will be done in WP4 will be linked to the general target of the SOLVE project.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

¹ Jobst, Nicola Michael, et al. "Ternary cathode blend electrodes for environmentally friendly lithium-ion batteries." *ChemSusChem* 13.15 (2020): 3928-3936.

² Schmaltz, Thomas, et al. "A Roadmap for Solid-State Batteries." *Advanced Energy Materials* 13.43 (2023): 2301886.